

THE IMPACT OF STRATEGIC PHYSIOGNOMY ELEMENTS ON ORGANIZATIONAL SUCCESS

Researcher: Karawan Azeez Hussain
Baghdad College for Economic Sciences University

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to identify the impact of strategic physiognomy and its elements on organizational success , After a brief literature review , an empirical study is conducted among university professors in Iraq which randomly selected . To this end , a model of the relation has been developed to be tested by regression and structural equation modeling . the result of this study shows that there is positive direct impact of strategic physiognomy on organizational success.

Keywords:

Strategic Physiognomy, Empowerment, Inspiration, Deep Understanding, Organizational Success, Structural Equation Modeling.

1. INTRODUCTION

All scales in the world including institutions, regions and the international arena have evolved to appreciate the idea that the world is running on a global economy controlled by the technology since 1950s (McCaffery, 2018). Further, the issue of globalization has penetrated the education sector, which is helping the schooling sector meet the needs of the learners while balancing the rate of globalization in the world. Currently, as stated by Johnson and other authors (2016), education has been significantly studied to be connected to growth of the economy, innovation and development of the social lives of the community. Further, connectivity and application of technological advancements have played a significant role in improving the education system in Iraq through inclusion of the strategic leadership, a sense of business and digital savvy (Søby, 2015).The only way to stay relevant in any field now days is by simply being competitive in any market or institution (McKee & Kagan,2016) and this cannot be achieved without the influence of some tools such as the strategic physiognomy and its dimensions. Strategic physiognomy is a tool that has been on constant use for the last 20 years and above, and it has been embraced by various companies and governments globally (Søby, 2015). From time immemorial competition has always exist and it is believed that good things happen in presence of competition. (Wartiovaara & Wincent, 2018), states that competitiveness is the act of a firm or an institution to produce or offer its products or services which meet the quality standards of the local or global market at the reasonable prices and provide adequate returns on the units of production that were employed. In this case, the dependent variable depends heavily on the independent variables which are also affected by various factors or dimensions. Therefore, the level of competitiveness that a firm has are directly proportional to how much they invest on the tool of strategic physiognomy (McKee & Kagan,2016).

The main reason for carrying out the literature review on the effect of “strategic physiognomy on organizational success is to take a closer look on the role that the strategic physiognomy plays on making sure that competitiveness in enhanced and organizational success. This review will dwell mainly on the far strategic physiognomy has improved competitiveness amid the presence of factors that influence or affect the tools. The factors are divided into two parts that is the dependent and independent variable. The dependent variable is organizational success whereas independent variables are strategic physiognomy.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW**2.1.Strategic Physiognomy**

It is a science based on systematic studies of the facial features and physical structure of the human being. This science is central to the emotions that are translated in the form of expressions that appear on the face of people, because mental activities and emotions affect the movement of muscles of the face thus directly reflects the psychological nature of the human being, and then the person can read the mind and analyze the personality (Castelli,2017) . This science has been organized into a set of theories that explain human nature based on a system of species that has been devised by observation. The origin of physiognomy is ancient and medieval. It was considered part of ancient scientific philosophy and was used as a means of detecting certain flaws. The beginning of the phonological documentation of the famous Greek philosopher Aristotle is attributed to the fact that he wrote a thesis in which he studies the features of the human face and the personal traits associated with these physical properties, such as the shape of the nose, eye color, The person and his attributes (Kleiner,2017).This science was used in the 18th and 19th centuries as a means of detecting a person's criminal tendencies. (Amy et al.,2018) Learning to learn If a person can learn phonology, he will become more successful in social relations. Psychologists confirm that 60% of human communication occurs Which appears in the form of physical movements or gestures in the face. Fruition can be learned by reading human features or by understanding facial and body movements and expressions.

The psychological theory used to describe the human personality and was defined by the 20th century Belgian teacher Paul Potts (Gibson,2002) .Consensus in its basic form corresponds to the definition of pseudo-science .This theory is based on phonetics, Principles for the study of symbols and geophysics. There is no clear evidence that physiognomy skills are real and can be acquired, although some recent studies have suggested that the human face "contains the nucleus of truth" through which human personality. Strategic physiognomy encompasses an act of observing personality traits of the individuals from facial appearances or features, dating back from Ancient Greece and continues to be popular in making decisions and judgments (Hassin & Tope, 2000). Most studies on physiognomy (Re & Rule,2015) have ascertained the correlation between personal characteristics or traits with physical differences, particularly individuals' facial features like; forehead and eyebrows, eyes and eyelids, nose, mouth and jaw, cheeks, chin, and ears and hair. Each of the facial features may indicate a meaning (Elena & Michael, 2010) and their combination may signal personalities like; conscientiousness, firmness, self-esteem, friendship, and benevolence; and even race or ethnicity. For example, Xiaolin et al. (2017) assessed the correlation between face images and personality traits and intelligence to establish whether individually reported intelligence and personality traits were predictable through face image and concluded that while personality traits could be predicted from face images, it is quite difficult to predict intelligence from face images. Although, the latter finding aligned with most previous studies (Re & Rule,2015); earlier study by Kleisner (2014) basing on facial images of 40 women and 40 men studying relation between perceived intelligence, measured IQ, and shape of faces, established that intelligence of men could be gauged but not women via facial images. This science is linked to two basic types: The first is things that cannot be returned to the scientific origins, but cannot be referred to only previous experiences of applicants, such as is found in the minds of humans, which is reflected clearly on their actions and faces. The second type is the science of inference, which exists in the nature of the shape and appearance in humans, through which can be identified through some of the secrets they have

According to litterateurs strategic physiognomy include three main elements or elements (Empowerment , Inspiration , Deep Understanding)(Wing,2015).as it shown in Figure 1.

Figure:1 Strategic Physiognomy Elements

2.2. Empowerment

The concept of empowerment has become clear after its introduction as a modern term. It means giving subordinates the right to participate in decision-making. In other words, the absence of central decision-making, but the centralization of any institution has no negative implications for development (Thompson & Kuvaas, 2017). In decision-making and freedom to act without satisfying the requirements of that right and the freedom to act. There have been clear and repeated references to many research and studies on the need for the organization to benefit from the knowledge, ideas, energy and creativity of all its employees (Kandampully et al., 2017), at the level of first-line workers, or managers at the level of managers to meet the global business environment, high expectations of customers and technology. Complex. Spreitzer (2008), noted that more than 70% of organizations have adopted at least some types of empowerment initiatives in part of their work, so research work in this area should be intensified to make use of it by local organizations

Empowerment is closely related to job satisfaction, meaning that the greater the level of managerial empowerment, the greater the sense of job satisfaction among workers (Fernandez & Moldogaziev, 2015). This result underlines the importance of managerial empowerment and a cycle of increased job satisfaction. Strengthening self-management through participation in decision-making rather than individual responsibility in making it would contribute to increased job satisfaction.

2.3. Inspiration

Mark Bayman (2013), a neuroscientist at Northwestern University, is studying "inspiration" as one of the most important factors in how the creative process works. Creativity in general is always interested in asking how new ideas come to the people. Inspiration, though important, is just a step in the process of creative process. Inspiration seems to occur when combined with serious analytical work (Bayman & Rigoletto, 2014). No one can discover the theory of relativity in a dream, if not a physicist who has done research, and analysis much about the same subject in advance. It is a tool to overcome internal or external pressure in response to exogenous pressures such as competition, deregulation, scarcity of resources, public demands, or the use of internal regulatory processes such as acquiring distinctive skills, reaching a high level of ambition, increasing the range and quality of services (Wartiovaara & Wincent, 2018), And this perspective is not consistent with the perspective of organizations as an open system.

2.4.Deep Understanding

Organizations began to realize the importance of strategic understanding and began to address their needs for this type of intelligence as they sought to harmonize it with the patterns of intelligence (emotional, competitive and business) and train their leadership to develop and effectively manage its elements (Fleisher & Bensoussan,2015). The strategic understanding of organizational leaders, As well as preparation to provide information to decision-makers and formulate strategies and plans in organizations in general and in service organizations in particular, as well as the understanding takes place among many topics of social capital and knowledge management systems and cultural (Cascio,2018). The determination of the strategy depends entirely on the organization's mission, capabilities, challenges and external opportunities. Informed decisions must be based on an in-depth understanding of the organization's capabilities and must reflect proper awareness to suit the organization and its environment.

2.5.Organizational Success

The concept of organizational success is a recent term in its expression within the literature of administrative thought and familiar in its elements which include the terms of effectiveness and efficiency together (Appiah et al.,2018). The organizational thought literature continued to address the problems of organizational performance by focusing on organizational success. Where the focus on the efficiency of the organization alone is no longer useful to judge the success of the organization, or focus on the effectiveness of the organization, but that the modern view includes a focus on organizational success, which includes efficiency and effectiveness together (Gomes et al.,2018).

Engelbart (2003) notes that successful organizations have many advantages because they are high performing because they outweigh the results of the strategies they have adopted and outperform their structures, processes and systems. Engelbart adds that successful organizations are characterized by their employees with a high understanding of their work, their commitment to achieve the results assigned to them, Working in the form of teams, low levels of negative conflicts, responsibility and their ability to solve problems away from underlying conflicts, and their continued pursuit of quality improvement (Geisler, & Wickramasinghe,2015).

The organizational success Variable is the quality of the organization that is efficient and effective. The successful organization is efficient and effective (Petrou et al.,2018). It can achieve its objectives and adjust to its environment in which it exploits the available resources and maximizes its outputs. According to (Zack,2010) organizational success can be measured by five elements (resources ,structure ,management, operation ,knowledge management).

3. METHODS AND MATERIALS

3.1.Procedures

The objective of this research is to analyze the relationship between strategic physiognomy and organizational success in public and private universities in Iraq. The analysis is made by segmenting by college, in such a way to establish the necessary correlations to obtain information that allows decisions to be made. To achieve the objective, a transversal, descriptive and correlational empirical study is developed. When analyzing the results of the study, it is necessary to take into account the population under study and the sample size. Thus, the field work has been carried out in a single university, so it can be considered exploratory. In addition, it has focused on professors from a personal point of view, of self-evaluation, so that the answers may be affected by trends. Accordingly a conceptual framework is shown in Figure 2.

Figure: 2 Conceptual Framework

3.2.Sample

The sample was chosen for this research corresponds to a total of 65 professors from public and private universities. The selection of this field of study is due to the need to provide relevant information that may favor a better management of this type of institution, because at the present time management in public and private education institutions is an important parameter for the analysis of the quality of the service delivered. To define the size of the sample, we worked with a 95% confidence, we used maximum variance and 5% error, which implied a random sample of 65 professors.

3.3.Instrument

The instrument of the study is a questionnaire, the data were collected by applying a self-response questionnaire and applied without altering the normal functioning of daily activities. Part I: strategic physiognomy questionnaire. To measure strategic physiognomy, we used a 10-items questionnaire with three elements (Table 1) developed and validated by (Wing,2016), which were based on the theory of (Reid,2016). With this instrument, we seek to know the dimensions of strategic physiognomy in this sample. Sample respond using a five-point Likert-type response format (from "Totally agree = 5" to "Strongly disagree = 1"). The valuations of the scales are obtained by means of the average of the values of the elements of each scale. Part II: organizational success questionnaire developed and validated by (Appiah et al.,2018). This instrument aims to measure the level of organizational success in in five dimensions with a total of 17 items (Table 1). Sample respond using a five-point Likert type response format.

Once the data were collected, it was necessary to organize, classify and summarize them adequately, in such a way that a better analysis of the information obtained was possible. To tabulate the data, a spreadsheet was used in Excel, then the statistical package SPSS 18.0. and Smartpls. The analyzes carried out, both strategic physiognomy and organizational success, correspond to the calculation of descriptive and analytical statistics and given the ordinal nature of the data.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Reliability

Reliability means what the coefficients of internal consistency indicate, that is, Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. What we want to check is whether each item measures the same dimension and if the responses tend to covariate, that is, if the subjects respond in a coherent way and in this way it can be deduced that the items express the same trait. (Tavakol & Dennick,2011) points out that it is usual to consider reliability coefficient

values of 0.50-0.60 as poor, between 0.60 - 0.70 as questionable, of 0.70-0.80 as acceptable and of 0.80-0.90 as good and 0.90 or above as excellent. Table 1 show the estimations of the internal consistency of the SP and OS scales. The reliability of the scales is variable and in all cases is adequate; these results are between 0.7 and 0.93, that is, the scales are consistent and acceptable.

Table: 1 Reliability of Strategic Physiognomy and Organizational Success Scales

Variable	No. of items	Cronbach's Alpha
UN	4	0.796
EM	3	0.723
IN	3	0.700
SP	10	0.831
RE	3	0.748
ST	4	0.809
MA	3	0.841
OP	3	0.815
KM	4	0.812
OS	17	0.931
All	27	0.939

4.2. Analysis of Correlations : Relationship between SP AND OS

Table 2 shows the correlations (Spearman's Rho correlation coefficient) between the dimensions of SP and OS. Regarding the relationship between the two variables studied, the results show positive and statistically significant correlations, Noting positive and statistically significant correlations between SP with the OS , which record (0.707) correlation coefficient and the significant value with less than (0.05). This could mean that when strategic physiognomy are used, it will improve the chance to the organizational success with (70.7%).the result support the first correlation hypothesis.

In regard to the dimensions the results that shown in Table 2 refer to positive and statistically significant correlations between UN and the OS , which record (0.487) correlation coefficient and the significant value with less than (0.05). This could mean that when UN are used, it will improve the chance to the organizational success with (48.7%).the result support the first correlation sub-hypothesis. Also there is positive and statistically significant correlations between EM and the OS , which record (0.719) correlation coefficient and the significant value with less than (0.05). This could mean that when EM are used, it will improve the chance to the organizational success with (71.9%).the result support the second correlation sub-hypothesis. And there is positive and statistically significant correlations between IN and the OS , which record (0.413) correlation coefficient and the significant value with less than (0.05). This could mean that when IN are used, it will improve the chance to the organizational success with (41.3%).the result support the third correlation sub-hypothesis.

Table: 2 Analysis of Correlations Results

	UN	EM	IN	RE	ST	MA	OP	KM	SP	OS
UN	1	.465**	.309*	.298*	.532**	.503**	.354**	.315*	.717**	.487**
		.000	.020	.026	.000	.000	.007	.018	.000	.000
EM	.465**	1	.521**	.578**	.603**	.678**	.594**	.542**	.889**	.719**
	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
IN	.309*	.521**	1	.234	.344**	.365**	.305*	.514**	.747**	.413**
	.020	.000		.082	.009	.006	.022	.000	.000	.002
RE	.298*	.578**	.234	1	.652**	.568**	.599**	.399**	.500**	.768**
	.026	.000	.082		.000	.000	.000	.002	.000	.000
ST	.532**	.603**	.344**	.652**	1	.818**	.754**	.469**	.636**	.899**
	.000	.000	.009	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
MA	.503**	.678**	.365**	.568**	.818**	1	.734**	.471**	.674**	.882**
	.000	.000	.006	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
OP	.354**	.594**	.305*	.599**	.754**	.734**	1	.689**	.554**	.907**
	.007	.000	.022	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
KM	.315*	.542**	.514**	.399**	.469**	.471**	.689**	1	.587**	.698**
	.018	.000	.000	.002	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
SP	.717**	.889**	.747**	.500**	.636**	.674**	.554**	.587**	1	.707**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
OS	.487**	.719**	.413**	.768**	.899**	.882**	.907**	.698**	.707**	1
	.000	.000	.002	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	

4.3. Analysis of the Effect: effect of SP on OS

The results of the analysis presented in Table 3 show that the effect hypothesis was supported. The existence of a relationship of significant statistical effect of the variable (SP) on (OS) ,According to F-value and P-value, the regression was significant , while F-calculated were greater than tabled F value, and ($p < 0.05$) at the study degree of freedom, consequently, the regression model as in the following equation:

$$OS = (0.547) + (0.855) (SP).$$

According to the values of regression coefficients ($B_0 = 0.547$) and ($B_1 = 0.855$) , it is clear that the change in the independent variable (SP) by one time will cause a change of 0.855 in the dependent variable of SP . Furthermore, the model interpreted (50%) of the change and variance that happened in the dependent variable. This result support the second main hypothesis .

Regarding the dimensions the simple regression results in table 3 show that there is significant statistical effect of the variable (UN) on (OS) ,According to F-value and P-value, the regression was significant , while F-calculated were greater than tabled F value, and ($p < 0.05$) at the study degree of freedom, consequently, the regression model as in the following equation:

$$OS = (1.737) + (0.551) (UN).$$

According to the values of regression coefficients ($B_0 = 1.737$) and ($B_1 = 0.551$) , it is clear that the change in the independent variable (UN) by one time will cause an increase of 0.551 in the dependent variable of OS . Furthermore, the model interpreted (23.7%) of the change and variance that happened in the dependent variable. This result support the first sub-hypothesis .

Also there is significant statistical effect of the variable (EM) on (OS) ,According to F-value and P-value, the regression was significant , while F-calculated were greater than tabled F value, and ($p < 0.05$) at the study degree of freedom, consequently, the regression model as in the following equation:

$$OS = (2.008) + (0.292) (EM).$$

According to the values of regression coefficients ($B_0 = 2.008$) and ($B_1 = 0.292$) , it is clear that the change in the independent variable (EM) by one time will cause an increase of 0.551 in the dependent variable of OS . Furthermore, the model interpreted (51.7%) of the change and variance that happened in the dependent variable. This result support the second sub-hypothesis .

Finally there is significant statistical effect of the variable (IN) on (OS) ,According to F-value and P-value, the regression was significant , while F-calculated were greater than tabled F value, and ($p < 0.05$) at the study degree of freedom, consequently, the regression model as in the following equation:

$$OS = (2.190) + (0.465) (IN).$$

According to the values of regression coefficients ($B_0 = 2.190$) and ($B_1 = 0.465$) , it is clear that the change in the independent variable (IN) by one time will result a change of 0.465 in the dependent variable of OS . Furthermore, the model interpreted (17%) of the change and variance that happened in the dependent variable. This result support the third sub-hypothesis .

Table:3 Simple Regression Results

Model	B	Std.Error	Beta	T	R	F	Sig
UN	1.737	0.602	0.551	4.097	0.237	16.783	0.000
EM	2.008	0.292	0.540	7.602	0.517	57.786	0.000
IN	2.190	0.604	0.465	3.328	0.170	11.077	0.002
SP	0.547	0.498	0.855	7.349	0.500	54.014	0.000
F (0.01) = 7.077				F (0.05) = 4.084			

One of the fundamental objectives of multivariate statistics techniques is increase the explanatory capacity of the empirical verification of the theory, or, to increase theoretical knowledge in cases where it is scarce. The models of structural equations are a multivariate data analysis technique of second generation that give a higher level of confidence to the research because of its statistical efficiency through powerful software ; its development has supposed in the field of empirical research, since it allows to examine simultaneously a series of dependency relationships between independent variables and dependents. These structural equation models can be used by researchers in the social sciences, education sciences, behavioral sciences, among others; they are often used in market research, they allow theoretically prove causal models (Byrne, 2016).

This statistical technique for series of simultaneous equation estimates through multiple regressions, it is characterized by two basic components: 1) the structural model and 2) the measurement model. The structural model is the guiding model which shows the dependency relationships between independent (exogenous) variables and dependent variables (endogenous). The measurement model shows the relationships between the constructs (latent variables) and the indicators (observable variables); in this model, the researcher can evaluate the contribution of each item (reactive) to the scale of measurement, that is, to specify which indicators define each construct. Further, evaluates the reliability of constructs and indicators (Hair et al.,2016).

In order to identify multiple relationships based on factors and items together, Smartpls are used to evaluate the model (Ringle et al. 2005). Relation coefficients are based on the coefficients of the path and R2. R2 is used to identify the explanatory power of the model. T statistics were used to identify the significance of the impact, and the significance of the paths. The results in Table 4 and Figure 2,3 indicate that the relationships are significant for all variables except IN. the direct effect of UN on OS is (0.214) with acceptable significant , and the direct effect of EM on OS is (0.595) with acceptable significant and (R2=0.560). And direct effect of the main variable SP on OS is (0.700) with acceptable significant and (R2=0.490).

Table: 4 Test the Hypotheses According to Smartpls

Path	B	Std.Error	T-Value	R2	Decision
UN...>OS	0.214	0.104	2.050	0.560	Supported
EM...>OS	0.595	0.136	4.358		Supported
IN...>OS	0.048	0.137	0.348		Unsupported
SP...>OS	0.700	0.052	13.521	0.490	Supported

Figure: 2 Effect of SP on OS according to SEM

Figure: 3 Effect of SP elements on OS according to SEM

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Every person seeks to achieve a set of goals and aspirations in his life. This is what drives him to harness all of the body, mind and spirit to serve these goals. He achieves his successes by searching for the three sources of strength (body / mind / spirit) . If each person sees himself, he will find a certain science, a specific body and a distinct mind, but with a different force, different and variable, And we seek all to reach creativity and excellence in one of these trends, but there are a number of mental disorders that fill our minds and emotions and our spirit in the pursuit of each of us to one of these sources and this prompts the person to search for a mechanism to get rid of these disorders, The symptoms of this are manifested by the large number of thinking, mood swings, contradictions, feelings of frustration, boredom, tension, etc. This is due to the lack of balance between the three elements (physical, mental and spiritual). And the lack of a way to control behaviors and reactions, or a system that creates harmony between the emotional side and the mental aspect of human, or practical exercises to change the negative side and the elimination of all weaknesses and the detection of sources of power in human and this is what we achieve through the various cycles of intelligence.

It is clear that it is important to employ the existing capacities of individuals in order to optimize the realization of the strategic physiognomy that gives insight into future actions and identify the pros and cons. This is what can be achieved through strategic physiognomy, which can provide organizational success factors. The standards of success are defined as those which are believed to show the impact of business, and they may be measurable quantitative criteria that reflect the purpose and mission of the organization, noting the importance of success measures as they provide feedings of underlying assumptions and rules (Kaplan & Norton, 1996) learn the bilateral loop, and the definition of success measures creates a common language and common thinking among working groups. What can be measured can be accomplished.

The objective of this research is to analyze the relationship between strategic physiognomy and organizational success, in private and public education institutions in Iraq and from the results obtained, we can conclude the following: In the relationship between the two main variables studied for this sample, the results show statistically significant correlations, The results indicated that there is an impact of strategic physiognomy on achieving organizational success, as well as on the level of sub-dimensions. It has been shown that there is a direct and positive effect of the empowerment variable on improving organizational success opportunities, The existence of the university as an independent educational institution that manages its own affairs is a progressive work that allows many achievements to emerge. These achievements are linked to the responsibility of each of its fields of work. Here lies the role of empowerment to promote this institution. The effective empowerment that meets the elements and benefits. Empowerment remains a mature and achievable educational area and theory, and it can change the modality of supervision positively, depending on serious and effective practice, and must be complementary. this result was supported by (Hanaysha,2016). As for the variable of inspiration, the results indicate that the effect is positive in organizational success. Providing inspiration to leaders and employees together and participating in decision making that allows participatory leadership will improve the strategic opportunities for efficiency and performance, thus contributing to organizational success. this result was supported by (Mooradian et al.,2016). Finally, the study proved that there is a positive impact of the deep understanding of organizational success. Successful leadership requires that there is an understanding of the internal and external environment with the ability to assess things before making decisions randomly.

REFERENCES

- [1] Amy Tikkanen, Swati Choper, Grace Young (2017), Physiognomy, Britannica.com, Retrieved 1/10/2018.
- [2] Appiah-Adu, K., Okpattah, B., & Amoako, G. K. (2018). Building Capability for Organizational Success: An Emerging Market Perspective. *Journal of African Business*, 19(1), 86-104.
- [3] Bayman, L., & Rigoletto, S. (2013). *Popular Italian Cinema*. Springer.
- [4] Byrne, B. M. (2016). *Structural equation modeling with AMOS: Basic concepts, applications, and programming*. Routledge.
- [5] Cascio, W. (2018). *Managing human resources*. McGraw-Hill Education.
- [6] Castelli, P. (2017). " Theophrastus depicts known human feelings". *The crisis of the theory of proportions: physiognomy, characters, affections*. *CRITICA LETTERARIA*, 45(4), 687-719.
- [7] Elena, V.S. & Michael, J. (2010). Making of a face: Role of facial physiognomy, skin tone, and color presentation made in evaluation of racial typicality. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 149 (1): pp.66-81.
- [8] Fernandez, S., & Moldogaziev, T. (2015). Employee empowerment and job satisfaction in the US Federal Bureaucracy: A self-determination theory perspective. *The American review of public administration*, 45(4), 375-401.
- [9] Fleisher, C. S., & Bensoussan, B. E. (2015). *Business and competitive analysis: effective application of new and classic methods*. FT Press.
- [10] Geisler, E., & Wickramasinghe, N. (2015). *Principles of Knowledge Management: Theory, Practice, and Cases: Theory, Practice, and Cases*. Routledge.
- [11] Gibson, M. (2002). *Born to crime: Cesare Lombroso and the origins of biological criminology*. Praeger Publishers.
- [12] Goetsch, D. L., & Davis, S. B. (2014). *Quality management for organizational excellence*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson.
- [13] Gomes, C. F., Najjar, M., & Yasin, M. M. (2018). Exploring competitive strategic performance consistency in service organizations. *Measuring Business Excellence*, 22(2), 165-182.
- [14] Hadrawi, H. K. (2018). Network Analysis of the Effect of Strategic Leadership on Organizational Success: Evidence from Iraqi Heavy Industry. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*.
- [15] Hair Jr, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2016). *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Sage Publications.
- [16] Hanaysha, J. (2016). Examining the effects of employee empowerment, teamwork, and employee training on organizational commitment. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 229, 298-306.
- [17] Hassin, R., and Tope, Y. (2000). Facing faces: Studies on the cognitive aspects of physiognomy. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 78 (5): 837-852.
- [18] Johnson, L., Becker, S. A., Cummins, M., Estrada, V., Freeman, A., & Hall, C. (2016). NMC horizon report: 2016 higher education edition (pp. 1-50). The New Media Consortium.
- [19] Kambiz, A. B. D. I., Mardani, A., Senin, A. A., Tupenaite, L., Naimaviciene, J., Kanapeckiene, L., & Kutut, V. (2018). The effect of knowledge management, organizational culture and organizational learning on innovation in automotive industry. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 19(1), 1-19.
- [20] Kandampully, J., Bilgihan, A., & Zhang, T. C. (2016). Developing a people-technology hybrids model to unleash innovation and creativity: The new hospitality frontier. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 29, 154-164.
- [21] Kleiner, Y. (2017). The Syllable according to Aristotle. *Histoire Epistémologie Langage*, 39(1), 137-153.
- [22] Kleisner, K., Chvatalova, V., Flegr, J. (2014). Perceived intelligence is associated with measured intelligence in men but not women. *PLoS ONE*, 9 (3): e81237.
- [23] McCaffery, P. (2018). *The higher education manager's handbook: effective leadership and management in universities and colleges*. Routledge.
- [24] McKee, G. J., & Kagan, A. (2016). Community bank product design within an asymmetric competitive market: an X-efficiency approach. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 34(5), 752-772.

- [25] Mooradian, T., Matzler, K., Uzelac, B., & Bauer, F. (2016). Perspiration and inspiration: Grit and innovativeness as antecedents of entrepreneurial success. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 56, 232-243.
- [26] Petrou, P., Demerouti, E., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2018). Crafting the change: The role of employee job crafting behaviors for successful organizational change. *Journal of Management*, 44(5), 1766-1792.
- [27] Re, D. E., & Rule, N. O. (2015). Appearance and physiognomy. *APA handbook of nonverbal communication*, 221-256.
- [28] Reid, J. (2016). Textual Physiognomy: A New Theory and Brief History of Dantean Portraiture. *California Italian Studies*, 6(1).
- [29] Ringle, C. M., Wende, S., & Will, A. (2005). *SmartPLS 2.0 M3*. Hamburg: University of Hamburg.
- [30] Sjøby, M. (2015). Finnish education system. *Nordic Journal of Digital Literacy*, 10(02), 64-68.
- [31] Spreitzer, G. M. (2008). Taking stock: A review of more than twenty years of research on empowerment at work. *Handbook of organizational behavior*, 2, 54-72.
- [32] Stacey, P. K., Morton, J., & Mohn, M. (2017). Building and maintaining strategic agility: a leadership agenda and framework for IT executives.
- [33] Tavakol, M., & Dennick, R. (2011). Making sense of Cronbach's alpha. *International journal of medical education*, 2, 53.
- [34] Thompson, G., Buch, R., & Kuvaas, B. (2017). Political skill, participation in decision-making and organizational commitment. *Personnel Review*, 46(4), 740-749.
- [35] Wartiovaara, M., Lahti, T., & Wincent, J. (2018). The role of inspiration in entrepreneurship: Theory and the future research agenda. *Journal of Business Research*.
- [36] Wing H., 2015, Strategic innovation and Physiognomy, *international journal of green studies* Vol.5 issue 20.
- [37] Xiaolin, W., and Zhang, X. (2016). Automated Inference on Criminality using Face Images. McMaster University and Shanghai Jiao Tong University.